

Error Performance of JPEG and Watermark Authentication Techniques in Wireless Sensor Network

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ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor network (WSN) is composed of tiny sensors and they are powered by energy-constraint battery. The continual need to utilize limited bandwidth to absorb most of the packets has led to a great deal of research in the field of data compression. WSN has been exploited to balance the maintenance of readable information content with acceptable error and the cost of energy consumed by the collecting nodes during the compression. In this paper, we compared two compression techniques: JPEG and watermark authentication. We applied both techniques and used error measurement to indicate system performance regardless of the number of execution instructions. We found that it is not enough to use error measurement only but the number of executing instructions must also be considered. The digital watermark approach showed a lower average error compared to JPEG approach. However, there were fewer instructions in the JPEG approach compared to watermark approach.

KEYWORDS

Wireless Sensor Network, Data Compression, Aggregation, JPEG, Security

1. INTRODUCTION

Advancements are emerging in the field of ad-hoc networks, and wireless sensor networks are no exception. Although these networks have achieved high performance and provide a practical environment for applications in this field, a great deal is still to be gained through the use of such technology. Understanding, knowledge, and experience will bring effective results and additional control to this technology; however, WSN suffer from problems, such as security and power consumption, on a variety of levels. Energy consumption is one of the major concerns in WSN. Such a restriction has motivated many researchers to look elsewhere in the network, such as at the node level, to save power; these results are reflected in the network's lifetime and efficiency [1]-[5]. We suggest a criterion for compression method utilization in order to compress raw data at the collecting sensor nodes before transmitting any information to the sink (base station).

Our contribution to the problem is to shed light on developing and finding better ways to use compression algorithms in WSN and to define a performance measurement depends on measuring

the error at the receiving end. It is important to keep in mind the number of steps used to compress raw data and decompress it at the sink in order to calculate power consumption in the network.

2. DATA COMPRESSION

In general, compression algorithms provide increased power efficiency and make room for more data in the memory; they are used in almost all aspects of wireless technology [6]. Bellare describes compression as occurring in two units [6]:

- 1- An encoding algorithm to process the signal or the raw data and provide a representation for the data in which it should be less than the original size.
- 2- A decoding algorithm to extract (reconstruct) the original signal and decompress the data at the destination.

Wireless sensor networks require compression algorithms because their sensors have limited memory and restricted power capacity [3]. A variety of effective compression algorithms are available; however, in the case of WSN, the choice is complicated because of these restrictions. For these reasons, it is difficult to implement some of the algorithms in WSN, where they will not serve the purposes of improving overall efficiency and optimizing battery life. The algorithms are divided into two categories:

- 1- Lossless compression - In which the information is compressed, sent, and uncompressed exactly as in the original state - not one bit is missing.
- 2- Lossy compression - It works under the same principles as lossless compression, except it does not compress the whole message; it does not compress very high frequency bits. Especially in pictures, the absence of high frequency bits will not damage the important content and the eye is still able to recognize the picture.

Both the nature of the application and the data affect the choice of which type of compression algorithm is applied in WSN. This does not mean that any changes should not be adjusted to the network's design to suit the purpose of the application. In general, most applications of WSN that use compression algorithms tend to use lossy compression because the requirements of the algorithm are considered moderate and not as high as the lossless requirements. In applications that need precision in transmitting and receiving data, text in particular, it is better to use lossless compression to avoid any chance of missing any part of it. Using lossy compression techniques on data that has text content is possible but with minimum tolerances [6]. One well-known example of lossy compression that we will use in this paper in association with WSN is JPEG (Joint Photographic Experts Group).

In WSN, when using applications that deploy compression algorithms, lossy compression is used to save energy, which means that some of the received data is missing. At this point, an error should be calculated to see how different the results are from the original data. This paper highlights the cases of two different compression algorithms, which are examined to determine their similarities and differences and to evaluate their performance. We measured performance by estimating the error in both systems.

In WSN, it is necessary to choose the algorithm that occupies less memory, has less access to the memory, and consumes less power. We use the average error as a performance measurement to

estimate the error resulting from the differences in data before and after transmission. The accuracy of the measurement performance is not perfect, but it provides a good guideline for making a decision. In order to compare two data compression techniques, we studied JPEG compression and a watermark-based approach by Wei Zhang [8]. Studying each system and understanding the equations for each technique, as well as applying some examples will help users to choose the best technique for their specific application and type of WSN.

Two important scientific terms need to be defined before moving forward. The first one is aggregation, which means organizing and minimizing repetition of information. Sometimes aggregation is just a simple mathematical operation. The second term is compression, which is the operation that describes the handling and processing of raw data to minimize its size in order to minimize the overhead when transmitting packets without affecting the overall purpose of the message.

2.1 Aggregation

The process of summarizing and combining data from sensor networks to minimize the load of data transmitted to a destination is called aggregation [10]. Some of the benefits of aggregating data before transmitting it include efficient utilization of the bandwidth and improvement of network performance. On the other hand, delays occur as a result of processing and sorting before the transmission, which affects the time consumed in aggregating data. Accuracy and security are other issues that researchers look forward to solving [11].

2.2 Secure Data Aggregation

Security is always a concern when it comes to WSN. Some of the issues in such networks occur because of attacks by hackers trying to take control of servers. The least damage that a hacker could cause is obtaining knowledge about the information that you are attempting to keep secure from the public—either because it involves privacy agreements or sensitive information. In some cases, the system is fully operational and no storage units or memories are affected by the attack; however, this is still viewed as a harmful action. The many studies and papers regarding secure data aggregation have led to a number of options for securing data with some tradeoffs; these should be considered carefully, depending on the application. To examine the subject of security more closely, we need to study the work of Zhang et al. [8], which uses digital watermarking as an authentication method for transmitted data and includes both aggregation and compression. Typically, security and data aggregation involves: (i) decrypting the data when it is received by the aggregators, (ii) aggregating the data according to the aggregating function, and (iii) encrypting the data before sending it forward to the next node.

2.3 Digital Watermarking

Watermarking technology is mainly used to protect copyright ownership. The main idea is to hide information within itself where the malicious node sees the data as noise [7]. In general, most watermarking generation systems consist of an embedder and a detector.

2.4 JPEG Compression

The JPEG standard is a well-known compression method based on Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). Using JPEG, the accuracy of the data at the receiving end is 8bits, and the elements in the quantized array are limited to 11bits [9]. This method is used in a number of different applications, depending on the type of JPEG compression preferred by the customer [9]. In general, JPEG has three baselines (1) a lossy baseline coding system, (2) an extended coding system, and (3) a lossless independent coding system. We have chosen the lossy baseline system, which depends on DCT. The compression sequences are (a) DCT computation, (b) quantization, and (c) variable-length code assignment.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for approaching the comparison is statistical, where the error is defined and applied to both methods to determine which method has less error. The watermark and JPEG approaches have similarities in their transforming methods. Their difference lies in quantization during the compressing process. In the watermark approach, the quantization uses a different method depending on K-largest coding. The methodology for approaching the comparison is statistical, where the error is defined and applied to both methods to determine which method has less error. In our research, the numbers of samples taken from each method are not equal because there is less sensory data from the watermark approach than from the JPEG approach. We substituted the missing elements with zeros to pad the rest of the array to fulfill the concept of 8*8 pixel blocks in the JPEG approach; the results were not as expected.

3.1 Error Calculation

The error estimation is used to estimate the differences in the samples to determine how the results deviate from the original value.

$$E = X_0 - X_1 \quad (1)$$

Where E represents the difference, X_0 represents the original sample before compressing, and X_1 represents the approximated value that is extracted at the receiving end. Making sure that the differences add up and preventing the effect of the polarity of the differences, we take the absolute value of the difference.

$$E = |X_0 - X_1| \quad (2)$$

The average or mean of the differences is expressed as:

$$M = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} |X_0 - X_1| \quad (3)$$

Here N represents the number of elements in the array. If we still want to relate the N to the dimensions of the array, then we have to make some modifications to Eq. (3) without affecting the results.

$$M = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \frac{1}{N} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \sum_{y=0}^{N-1} |X_0 - X_1| \quad (4)$$

The Eq. (4) is more practical than the first one, because of the simplicity of using the same parameters. It is still useful to use the Eq. (3), but we have to make sure that we use the number of elements in the array not the number of bits. We used discrete cosine transform `dct2 ()` function of the Matlab® to save time and make calculations faster and easier. This tool quickly calculates the discrete cosine transform. We only need to enter the array and the tool will compute the coefficient array.

4. ANALYSIS OF ERRORS

Understanding the error as a performance metric regardless of the number of execution stages is the core of this research. Based on the definition of the error measurement in the previous section, the array of differences in each method showed almost the same results, with small differences. In addition, the calculations in the watermark approach were performed with an unequal number of samples, an equal number of samples, and in another case, the same data was used in both approaches.

4.1 Unequal Number of Samples

4.1.1 JPEG Approach

JPEG is a lossy image compression technique [12]. Fig. 1 shows the different stages for the image compression technique using JPEG.

Figure 1: JPEG data compression technique

Let us assume that we have the following 8 x 8 input matrix as given in [9], [12].

$$Input = \begin{bmatrix} 52 & 55 & 61 & 66 & 70 & 61 & 64 & 73 \\ 63 & 59 & 55 & 90 & 109 & 85 & 69 & 72 \\ 62 & 59 & 68 & 113 & 144 & 104 & 66 & 73 \\ 63 & 58 & 71 & 122 & 154 & 106 & 70 & 69 \\ 67 & 61 & 68 & 104 & 126 & 88 & 68 & 70 \\ 79 & 65 & 60 & 70 & 77 & 68 & 58 & 75 \\ 85 & 71 & 64 & 59 & 55 & 61 & 65 & 83 \\ 87 & 79 & 69 & 68 & 65 & 76 & 78 & 94 \end{bmatrix}$$

After using the JPEG compression techniques mentioned in [9] and [12], we will get the following output matrix as given in [9] and [12].

$$Output = \begin{bmatrix} 58 & 64 & 67 & 64 & 59 & 62 & 70 & 78 \\ 56 & 55 & 67 & 89 & 98 & 88 & 74 & 69 \\ 60 & 50 & 70 & 119 & 141 & 116 & 80 & 64 \\ 69 & 51 & 71 & 128 & 149 & 115 & 77 & 68 \\ 74 & 53 & 64 & 105 & 115 & 84 & 65 & 72 \\ 76 & 57 & 56 & 74 & 75 & 57 & 57 & 74 \\ 83 & 69 & 59 & 60 & 61 & 61 & 67 & 78 \\ 93 & 81 & 67 & 62 & 69 & 80 & 84 & 84 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now, the error matrix based on Eq. (1) is as follows:

$$Error = \begin{bmatrix} -6 & -9 & -6 & 2 & 11 & -1 & -6 & -5 \\ 7 & 4 & -1 & 1 & 11 & -3 & -5 & 3 \\ 2 & 9 & -2 & -6 & -3 & -12 & -14 & 9 \\ -6 & 7 & 0 & -4 & -5 & -9 & -7 & 1 \\ -7 & 8 & 4 & -1 & 1 & 4 & 3 & -2 \\ 3 & 8 & 4 & -4 & 2 & 11 & 1 & 1 \\ 2 & 2 & 5 & -1 & -6 & 0 & -2 & 5 \\ -6 & -2 & 2 & 6 & -4 & -4 & -6 & 10 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now, we compute M, which is the average error from Eq. (4). We chose 8*8 to reflect the dimension of the array, and since we are on the verge of calculating a group of average errors, we sub-numbered the M in each case to differentiate between them. The average error is:

$$M_1 = \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{8} \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^7 |X_0 - X_1| = \frac{310}{64} = 4.84375.$$

4.1.2 Watermark Approach

The watermark authentication approach is shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2: Watermarking technique [8]

The error matrix $E=|X_0-X_1|$ is calculated by subtracting the restored data from the original sensing data of Fig. 2.

-3	1	2	-3	-2	1	-2	-2
1	-1	1	-1	-2	4	-1	2
3	-1	4	3	2	1	-2	1
2	2	2	2	-1	2	3	-2

The average error is:

$$M_2 = \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{4} \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^3 |X_0 - X_1| = \frac{62}{32} = 1.9375.$$

By comparison, $M_1 < M_2$, which means that there were fewer errors in the watermark approach than in the JPEG approach. The inequality in the number of data samples may be the reason for this margin in error measurement. Next, we will see another comparison where the same number of samples is compared to eliminate inequality from the calculation.

4.2 Equal Number of Samples

We assume the number of samples in each method is equal. In this scenario, we drop some samples into the JPEG approach for the sake of equality and fairness in the comparison.

4.2.1 JPEG Approach

In this case, we consider only the first 32 elements of the error array; in this case, there are 8 columns and 4 rows.

-6	-9	-6	2	11	-1	-6	-5
7	4	-1	1	11	-3	-5	3
2	9	-2	-6	-3	-12	-14	9
-6	7	0	-4	-12	-9	-7	1

We compute the average error M_3 as:

$$M_3 = \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{4} \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^3 |X_0 - X_1| = \frac{184}{32} = 5.75$$

After reducing the number of samples in the JPEG approach, we found $M_3 < M_2$, which means the result is in favor of the watermark approach. Under the same category of equal samples, different data were used in the two approaches. Similar data sources were used.

4.2.2 Applying JPEG on Watermark Data

We have only 32 elements in the watermark based sensor data. We added extra 32 elements with zeros to form an 8x8 matrix for JPEG operation. First 32 elements were collected from the original sensing data of Fig. 2.

20	21	21	20	18	22	19	23
21	24	24	21	20	24	21	19
25	28	24	23	23	25	26	30
28	26	25	23	28	25	28	32
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

We also consider the gray levels are already subtracted. The two dimensional DCT computation of the above coefficient array can be done by using the following equation:

$$G_{u,v} = \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^7 \alpha(u)\alpha(v)g_{x,y} \cos\left[\frac{\pi}{8}\left(x + \frac{1}{2}\right)u\right] \cos\left[\frac{\pi}{8}\left(y + \frac{1}{2}\right)v\right]$$

After apply the DCT, the output array T (u,v) resulting from the application of the Matlab[®] function is as follows:

91.7500	0.9946	5.3519	-5.0868	1.7500	-1.4188	-2.7580	2.5975
79.2008	1.5400	3.5438	-4.2670	0.1933	-1.0152	-1.4815	0.9361
-8.8029	0.7675	-3.4911	1.8894	-3.7023	0.4686	3.5141	-4.0124
-34.3927	-1.8181	-5.2110	5.7755	-4.2086	0.3230	6.3907	-5.5238
3.0000	-3.8253	-0.6437	3.9651	-0.5000	-0.9071	4.3256	-2.3340
23.7825	-2.2670	3.9649	-1.8538	3.6373	-0.9951	-1.0810	1.8085
-2.3069	1.4897	4.2641	-6.4280	4.7807	0.3436	-5.2589	3.3341
-22.1054	2.7594	1.9987	-5.6114	2.9826	1.0238	-4.7030	2.1797

It is necessary to round the array elements of T (u,v) to the nearest integer.

92	1	5	-5	2	-1	-3	3
79	2	4	-4	0	-1	-2	1
-9	1	-4	9	-4	1	4	-4
-34	-2	-5	6	-4	0	6	-6
3	-4	-1	4	-1	-1	4	-2
-23	-2	4	-2	4	-1	-1	2
-2	2	4	-6	5	0	-5	3
-22	3	2	-6	3	1	-5	2

The next step is quantization. The coefficient array is ready to be quantized. A quantizing array Z (u,v) for the JPEG compression is defined as [9].

16	11	10	16	24	40	51	61
12	12	14	19	26	58	60	55
14	13	16	24	40	57	69	56
14	17	22	29	51	87	80	62
18	22	37	56	68	109	103	77
24	35	55	64	81	104	113	92
49	64	78	87	103	121	120	101
72	92	95	98	112	100	103	99

We must divide each element from $T(u,v)$ by the corresponding element from $Z(u,v)$ to obtain the quantized array $\hat{T}(u,v)$.

$$\hat{T}(u,v) = \text{round} \left[\frac{T(u,v)}{Z(u,v)} \right]$$

6	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

At this encoding stage, a zigzag reordering of $\hat{T}(u,v)$ is [6 0 7 0 0 1 0 0 0 -2 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 -1 EOB].EOB means End of Blocks, where the rest of the blocks after it are all zeros.

The reverse transformation has to take place in order to retrieve the input data at the destination. The attention will be concentrated on the decoding, dequantization and the reverse of the coefficient array. Dequantization starts with the construction of the quantized array from the one-dimensional array, above which is another form of the two-dimensional quantized array.

The next step is to reconstruct the approximation of the coefficient array $\hat{T}(u,v)$ according to the following equation:

$$\hat{T}(u,v) = \hat{T}(u, v) Z(u, v)$$

96	0	10	0	0	0	0	0
84	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-28	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
-24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The last step in the reverse process is to reverse the approximation coefficient array $\hat{T}(u,v)$.

21.7245	20.7678	19.4148	18.4581	18.4581	19.4148	20.7678	21.7245
31.1067	30.1500	28.7970	27.8403	27.8403	28.7970	30.1500	31.1067
25.9099	24.9532	23.6002	22.6435	22.6435	23.6002	24.9532	25.9099
15.7525	14.7957	13.4428	12.4860	12.4860	13.4428	14.7957	15.7525
11.5140	10.5572	9.2043	8.2475	8.2475	9.2043	10.5572	11.5140
1.3565	0.3998	-0.9532	-1.9099	-1.9099	-0.9532	0.3998	1.3565
-3.8403	-4.7970	-6.1500	-7.1067	-7.1067	-6.1500	-4.7970	-3.8403
5.5419	4.5852	3.2322	2.2755	2.2755	3.2322	4.5852	5.5419

This is the outcome of the Matlab[®] reverse transformation function. The results must now be rounded to the nearest integer.

22	21	19	19	19	19	21	22
31	30	29	28	28	29	30	31
26	25	24	23	23	24	25	26
16	15	13	13	13	13	15	16
12	11	9	8	8	9	11	12
1	0	-1	-2	-2	-1	0	1
-4	-5	-6	-7	-7	-6	-5	-4
6	5	3	2	2	3	5	6

The results shown above are the data retrieved from the source; it is an approximation (the original plus changes).

The error array is shown below. It is the difference between the original array and the retrieved array at the destination. We consider the absolute value for each element in the array.

2	0	2	1	1	3	2	1
10	6	5	7	8	5	9	12
1	3	0	0	0	1	1	14
12	11	12	10	15	12	13	16
12	11	9	8	8	9	11	12
1	0	1	2	2	1	0	1
4	5	6	7	7	6	5	4
6	5	3	2	2	3	5	6

After the array of differences has been obtained, we can compute the average error as follows.

$$M_4 = \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{1}{8} \sum_{x=0}^7 \sum_{y=0}^7 |X_0 - X_1| = \frac{368}{64} = 5.7.$$

After calculating the average error for the four different cases, it is obvious that the results favor the watermark approach, but not enough to determine which approach is better in terms of less error measurement. Moreover, M_4 resulted in an answer that was not much different from the

others. On the other hand, M_4 behaved differently than M_1 . We also found that $M_4 > M_1$ although M_4 and M_1 are supposed to be almost the same.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We employed two compression algorithms in a wireless sensor network to determine if there were any significant changes in performance in terms of error measurement. We concluded that depending only on the error measurement to assess the performance of a network is not adequate. Our results led to small error margins and a slight preference in favor of the watermark approach. It is better to use a compression method that utilizes quantization methods that depend on K-largest coding, as suggested by Zhang, rather than the quantization methods used in the JPEG approach, which depend on the Human Visual System. The average error between the two approaches was very small. However, in WSN, algorithms with less error should be used in order to save energy and to conserve memory. In this paper, we explained the reasons for employing compression algorithms in WSN and how they contribute to the performance of the entire network. WSN is getting smaller and requiring less power than ever before, which demands more attention and careful choices of the type and size of software on the chip. The need for deploying of compression method in WSN is increasing due to the requirement of new application that process more information. In that sense, compatible compression methods are a necessity in WSN environments.

In the future, we will concentrate on quantization methods. The criteria will depend on the number of instructions and the error measurement, where the number of instructions is related to power consumption. This is a massive area of research. To enhance the security of WSN, it is required to look into transformation techniques to cover every aspect of lossy compression as well as other WSN compatible compression methods.

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